

Notes

Radiation Protective Agents : Synthesis of Some N'-substituted mercapto alkyl guanidines, Isothiuronium salts and Thiosulphuric acid derivatives I.

P. G. AGNIHOTRI and J. P. TRIVEDI*

M. G. Science Institute, Ahmedabad 380 009

Manuscript received 18 October 1976, revised 15 April 1977,
accepted 13 July 1977

AMINOTHIOLS exhibit very remarkable radiation protective property. Patt¹ in 1949 discovered the radiation protective property of cysteine in mice. In 1951, Bacq et al² reported the effectiveness of cysteamine (MEA) and cystamine—the decarboxylation products of cysteine and cystine respectively. 3-Mercaptopropylamine (MPA) and 4-mercaptobutylamine (MBA) have also been shown to possess anti-radiation property³. Doherty et al⁴ introduced aminoethyl isothiuronium bromide hydrobromide (AET) in 1955, pointing out its superiority to other thiols, particularly in respect of its effectiveness after oral administration, the simplicity of synthesis and its stability on storage. This compound rearranges *in vivo* to 2-mercaptoethyl guanidine (MEG) which seems to be responsible for its radiation protective property. Various N'-Alkyl derivatives of MEG have been synthesised and tested by Shapira et al⁵. When the thiol group in the aminothiols is replaced by a thiosulphate group, Bunte salts are obtained which equalled the parent compound in their protective activity, but such compounds are much less toxic. For example, 5-2-aminoethyl-thiosulphuric acid is a well-known radioprotector⁶.

In the present communication, synthesis of some N-Aryl-N'-(ω -mercapto) alkyl guanidines, their corresponding isothiuronium salts and thiosulphuric acid derivatives have been described. The aromatic guanidines prepared from substituted anilines with the help of S-Methyl isothiurea sulphate, were treated with excess of α -W-dibromo alkanes in presence of pyridine to yield N-Aryl-N'-(ω -bromo) alkyl guanidines(I). These with sodium hydrogen sulphide and thiourea afforded N-Aryl-N'-(ω -mercapto)alkyl guanidines(II) and isothiuronium salts (IV) respectively. The thiosulphuric acids(III) were obtained by treating the hydrobromide salts of bromoalkylguanidines (I) with sodium thiosulphate. (Figure 1).

Fig. 1.

Experimental proof for the structure of N-Aryl-N'-(ω -mercapto)alkyl guanidines (II) was provided by two other routes depicted in Figure 2.

Fig. 2.

* Present address : R. & D Department, Cadila Laboratories, Ahmedabad-380 008.

NOTES

Experimental

Preparation of N-arylguanidines: The mixture of S-methylisothiurea sulphate (0.3 mole) and pure amine (0.6 mole) was heated to a temperature of 150° - 170° by means of an oil bath. In some cases, where water was used as a solvent, the mixture was refluxed. Methyl mercaptan evolved was absorbed in 20% solution of NaOH. The heating was continued until there was no

further evolution of methyl mercaptan. The solid mass obtained was intimately incorporated with 95% ethanol and allowed to stand for 24 hours. The solid guanidine sulphate containing some amine sulphate was filtered off, washed with little cold water and dried. Purification was done by converting sulphate into carbonate using Ba(OH)₂ and CO₂. The yield was about 55-60% of the theoretical.

TABLE 1: R - C₆H₄ - NH - C(=NH) NH(CH₃)_nX

R	n	m.p.(I)* [X=Br]	n.p.(II)** [X=SH]	m.p.(III)** [X=S.SO ₂ H]	m.p.(IV)** [X=SC(=NH)NH ₂ .HBr]
H	2	118	126	105	116
H	3	119	123	103	107
H	4	121	128	97	104
4-CH ₃	2	155	143	207	128
"	3	147-148	144	183	129
"	4	151-53	141	219	142
4-OCH ₃	2	148	140	211	150
"	3	152	144	214	137
"	4	143	118	209	132
4-OH	2	212-15(d)	173	236(d)	154
"	3	219	164	310(d)	69
"	4	325	151-52	295(d)	81-82
4-Cl	2	140	127	202	125
"	3	137	136	288	117
"	4	136	141	177	124
4-Br	2	132	129	177	107
"	3	140	131	304(d)	126
"	4	122	129	195(d)	121
4-N(CH ₃) ₂	2	130	99	119	95
"	3	129	118	117	64
"	4	127	126	156	101
4-NHCOCH ₃	2	137-38	179	298(d)	189
"	3	294-(d)	158-60	314(d)	140
"	4	142-43	149	294	190

*N and Br. analysed and found to be within experimental limits.

**N and S " " "

Preparation of N-aryl, N'(ω -bromo)alkyl guanidines : I. The appropriate guanidine sulphate (0.1 mole) α - ω dibromoalkane (0.2 mole) and pyridine (0.15 mole) were refluxed by means of an oilbath for a period of about 3 to 4 hours. The mixture was then poured in ice-cold water. The aqueous layer was separated and washed with ether. It was then neutralized by adding sodium bicarbonate. Free base was separated as precipitates upon vigorous scratching. It was then filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized from ethanol. The yield was in the range of 55-70% of the theoretical amount.

Preparation of N-aryl, N'(ω -mercapto)alkyl guanidine : II. N-aryl-N'(ω -bromo)alkyl guanidine (0.01 mole) and sodium hydrogen sulphide (0.01 mole) were dissolved in ethanol and the mixture was refluxed for about half an hour on water-bath. Sodium bromide separated on cooling, was filtered off and the filtrate on standing gave the crystals of the mercapto compound. It was filtered, dried and recrystallized from rectified spirit. The yield was about 70% of the theoretical amount.

Preparation of N-aryl, N'(ω -thiosulphuro) alkyl guanidines (Bunte Salts) : III. The hydrobromide salt of N-aryl, N'(ω -bromo)alkyl guanidine (0.01 mole) and sodium thiosulphate crystals (0.01 mole) were dissolved in slightly more than the required amount of warm water, then refluxed for about half an hour and filtered. The crystals of the Bunte salt were obtained on cooling. The yield was about 80-90% of the theoretical amount.

Preparation of Isothiuronium salts : IV. Equimolar amounts of N-aryl, N'(ω -bromo)alkyl guanidine and thiourea were dissolved in ethanol and the mixture was refluxed for about 15 minutes on water-bath. The solution was then concentrated to half of its volume, cooled and diluted with equal volume of ethyl acetate. The mixture was then chilled, stirred and scratched to give the crystals of isothiuronium salt.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. J. J. Trivedi, Principal, M. G. Science Institute, Ahmedabad-9 for his help and active interest in the work.

References

1. H. M. PATT, E. B. TYREE, R. I. STRAUBLE and D. E. SMITH, *Science*, 1949, 110, 213.
2. Z. M. BACQ, A. HERVE, J. LECOMTE, P. FISCHER, J. BIARIER, G. DECHAMPS, H. LE BEHAN and P. RAYET, *Arch. Interim. Physiol.*, 1951, 59, 442.
3. D. G. DOHERTY, W. T. BURNETT JR. and R. SHAPIRA, *Radiation Research*, 1957, 7, 13.
4. D. G. DOHERTY and W. T. BURNETT JR., *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1955, 89, 312.
5. R. SHAPIRA, D. G. DOHERTY and W. T. BURNETT JR., *Radiation Research*, 1957, 7, 22-34.
6. HOLMBERG and B. SORBO, *Nature (London)*, 1959, 183, 832.

7. C. P. JOSHNA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 37, 621.
8. D. G. DOHERTY and R. J. SHAPIRA, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, 28, 1339.

Palladium(II) Complexes of α -Oximino-acetoacetarylamide Benzoylhydrazones

M.M. PATEL*, M.R. PATEL & B.N. MANKAD

Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University,
Vallabh Vidyanagar-388 120, Gujarat

Manuscript received 13 October 1976, revised 22 March 1977,
accepted 13 July 1977

IN continuation of our previous work on synthesis of α -oximino- β -hydrazinoacetoacetarylamides¹, their analytical aspects²⁻⁴ and Pd(II) complexes⁵, the present paper deals with the preparation and characterisation of Pd(II) complexes with α -oximinoacetoacetarylamide benzoylhydrazones.

Experimental

Preparation of the complexes : 10 ml. aq. solution of Pd(II) chloride (0.05 M) was gradually added to 25 ml alcoholic solution (2%) of α -oximinoacetoacetylchloroanilide benzoylhydrazone and acidified with dil. HCl. The mixture was diluted to about 100 ml with distilled water and digested on waterbath for half an hour; the bright yellow precipitates obtained were filtered, washed with hot water and aq. ethanol (1:1), and dried in an oven at 110°.

The Pd(II) complexes of the other α -oximinoacetoacetarylamide benzoylhydrazones of the series were prepared in the same manner. The m.p., colour, elemental analysis and composition of the complexes are given in Table-1. The infrared spectra of the ligands and complexes and the electronic spectra of the ligands in ethanol solution were recorded.

Results and Discussion

Electronic spectra of the ligands : The chromophoric system N=C-C-C=O in the ligands exhibits two

bands, one at 230-35 nm (C=18500-27400) and second at 275-79 nm (C=16500-20300). Comparison of these spectra with those of acetoacetarylamide benzoylhydrazones with chromophoric system, N=C-CH₂-C=O (Band I, 250-258 nm, C=15100 to 26400, Band II, 229-230 nm, C=16100 to 17200)⁶ reveals that there is hypsochromic effect (Δ C=1800-3900) in Band I and there is a bathochromic displacement of the Band II to the extent of 46-50 nm, without appreciable change in intensity.